

ASSESSMENT OF THE DENTAL CONDITION OF MILK TEETH UNDER THE INFLUENCE OF HORMONAL DRUGS USED DURING THE FETAL PERIOD

Mirsalixova F. L

Professor

Abdirimova Gulrux Ibadullayevna

Abstract: This article pays special attention to research aimed at improving the treatment of enamel hypoplasia in children, which occurs as a result of hormonal preparations in pregnancy. In this, measures are taken to determine the clinical-functional features of the specific course of diseases that develop in children as a result of hormonal preparations in pregnancy, associated with diseases of the oral cavity in modern dentistry.

Keywords: Enamel hypoplasia, physiotherapeutic measures, clinical-dental, laboratory, immunological and statistical methods.

Scientific sources noted that "studies over the past twenty years have shown that pregnancy is caused by hormonal drugs, enamel hypoplasia in children is up to 42%, and these diseases, along with various syndromes, up to 30%". This situation is explained by the fact that the initial stages of diseases are accompanied by an absence of sufficient data on changes in both clinical and laboratory tests, as well as the absence of a single etiopathogenetic view among specialists. This indicates the need to improve the treatment and Prevention of the problem.

At the global level, special attention is paid to research aimed at improving the treatment of enamel hypoplasia in children, which occurs as a result of hormonal preparations in pregnancy. In this, it is important to determine the clinical and functional features of the specific course of diseases associated with oral diseases in modern dentistry, which develop in children as a result of hormonal preparations in pregnancy; assess the place of dental and physiotherapeutic measures in the complex treatment process; develop a comprehensive step-by-step approach plan that takes into account the somatic condition of children.

It is known that the norm of the number of teeth for adults is 32. Why do children have only 20 of them? The fact is that at the age of 6 months, when the baby's first teeth begin to come out, his jaw is very small. As the child grows, it is lengthened. And during the gliding period, two pairs of teeth additionally appear on each jaw. They are called premolars and are among the loci and molars. As a result, the number of Teeth Increases from 20 to 28. And Where are the remaining 4? These are called wisdom teeth, and they grow much later after 17 years.

The tooth replacement process is basically painless. It turns out that the roots of temporary teeth, canines and molars dissolve in a certain period. As a result, milk teeth lose their support, loosen and fall out one after the other. They are replaced by molars, which have a denser structure, hard enamel and more resistance to temporary teeth. Thus, the child's body adapts to adult food. The procedure for losing milk

teeth in children, the scheme and time of this process are presented below. Due to some signs, it can be determined that the process of losing a child's milk teeth will begin soon:

The gaps between the teeth are increasing. Due to the stretching of the growing jaw, temporary teeth, canines and molars are located at an increasing distance from each other. The reason for contacting a dentist is that the child is already six years old, and the intervals remain unchanged. A special scheme for the loss of milk teeth in children has been developed in order to smear parents from a point of view. It describes the age and sequence of the substitution.

Milk tooth shake. About two years before the onset of temporary tooth decay, the loss of dogs and molars, their roots begin to Melt. This process has changed to the touch neck, the latter of which gradually begins to vibrate.

- Permanent tooth protrusion next to the milk tooth. Sometimes it happens that a temporary incision, dog or molar has not yet fallen, and its root heir is already visible nearby. Dentists consider this phenomenon harmless. And if a permanent tooth erupts and the milk located next to it does not fall out within three months, you should consult a dentist.

Let's see how molars are replaced in children: at what age to lose? What is a change scheme? And how long will this process take? Experts say that the time for each child is individual. The total duration of the transformation of cuttings, molars and canines is from six to eight years. On average, the onset of loss of "milk teeth" in girls is about six years old, in boys a little later. However, current children are developing rapidly. Therefore, the pattern of losing milk teeth in children can be attributed to the age of five. Also, the date of the beginning of the process of caesarean section, molar and tooth transformation and its duration depend on the genetic heredity of the child. This affects climatic conditions, eating habits and the quality of drinking water.

Below is a graphical representation of the primary milk tooth replacement sequence in children. The fall scheme, the image of which is attached, shows that first the incisors, then the first molars, then the turn of the Dogs comes to the last second molars in the sheet. At the age of six or seven, when the process of replacing milkmen begins, the central incisor teeth fall out in the first place. And first of all it happens with the teeth of the lower jaw. In addition, the lateral incisors located on the upper jaw fall out, followed by the same lower teeth. They change when the child is seven or eight years old. Then the scheme for losing milk teeth in children involves changing the first molars of the upper and lower jaws. This happens at the age of nine or eleven.

Then, from nine to twelve years old, by default, the teeth of the upper jaw should fall out, after which the same teeth from the lower part. The last, as evidenced by the pattern of losing milk teeth in children, is the second molars of the lower jaw, and then the upper one. This happens at the age of ten or twelve. Milk teeth are more susceptible to the negative effects of caries than molars. And the complications of this disease occur very often. The child himself cannot realize that the tooth enamel is damaged. That is, a visit to the dentist is necessary for the diagnosis of caries. Parents should be very responsible in this regard. After all; advanced diseases of the axillary milk teeth are the direct path to their loss, which in itself is a bad factor. Temporary incisors, canines, and molars are the "Guardians" of the site to replace their position. In the event of the loss of a temporary tooth, it is necessary to fill the space in which its neighbors appear.

A good pediatric dentist will never allow you to remove a milk tooth if it can be treated and maintained. However, there are cases when it is indispensable. Obtaining a temporary tooth is justified in the following cases:

- Serious destruction of the " milk bottle " and the impossibility of its restoration.
- The presence of a basal cyst of a temporary tooth.

- The development of inflammation, which can later lead to problems with molar.
 - Permanent tooth protrusion when the milk tooth does not fall out.
 - Severe splashes of milk cutter, dog or molar, which cause pain and discomfort to the child.
- 1) Above, age limits, loss patterns have been identified in which milk teeth are replaced in children. 5 years is a time limit, followed by loss, despite the fact that the norm of the onset of temporary tooth changes in mediatic dentistry is considered to be that the child is six years old, an incision, dog or molar is no longer considered premature. The reasons for the premature loss of milk bottles can be:
 - 2) Injury. The child lost his tooth as a result of mechanical impact (fall, shock).
 - 3) Abnormal bite, which is defined by the term "deep" in Pediatric Dentistry. The upper jaw covers the lower jaw, which is exposed to excessive pressure and is likely to lose them.
 - 4) Attack of neighboring teeth. This happens when the " milkers" grow incorrectly. The cause of early prolapse is similar to the previous paragraph - a temporary incision, excessive pressure on the dog or molar.
 - Caries in neglected condition. In this case, the milk tooth simply decomposes. * Intentional loosening of temporary teeth, dog or molar teeth by the child.

There is a situation when milk teeth are not in a hurry to fall out. This can be due to the child's heredity, severe infectious disease, rickets in the baby or an unbalanced diet, and, as a result, a lack of vitamins and potassium in the body. The option is possible when the milk tooth has not yet fallen out and its root replacement begins next to it. This is called shark teeth. There is nothing wrong, lekinfat in three months only if the " milk jug " allows a permanent tooth. Otherwise, a visit to the dentist is necessary. It is also necessary to visit the dentist if the child has reached the age of eight and the milk teeth are still in place.

Usually, the loss of a milk tooth occurs before its growth, so for a child such a moment is not surprising. Once a temporary dog, incision, or molar has disappeared, a scar forms at the site of its growth. A sterile cotton swab or gauze should be applied to the hole to stop the blood. Bleeding stops after 3-5 minutes. Within 2 hours after falling, you should not feed the child, and after this time you should take hot food of a homogeneous composition for two to three days. In order not to injure the unprotected gum area, solid components and large parts must be removed. Rinse your mouth gently after eating. The blood clots that form where the tooth is lost will fall off on their own in two to three days. It is strictly forbidden to take it mechanically.

After the " milk tooth " has fallen out, the child should not be allowed to bite extremely hard foods such as nuts, crackers, caramel. The use of antiseptic agents (hydrogen peroxide or alcohol solutions) for cauterization is also prohibited. Do not touch the hole through which the blood is flowing with your fingers to prevent infection. If the child has a fever after a temporary incision, loss of a dog or molar, this is a reason to immediately consult a pediatrician. And during the period of replacement of milk teeth, you should consult a dentist for a preventive examination at least twice a year. At what age does the diagram of milk teeth in children fall out To keep milk teeth healthy and healthy, the following are recommended:

- Brush your teeth twice a day with a soft brush.
- Teach the baby to rinse his mouth every time he eats.
- Include milk and sour milk products in your child's diet to enrich the body with Kaltsiy.

During the period of temporary changes in teeth, canines and molars in a baby, adults ask themselves such questions: when do molars begin to be replaced in children? Is the drawing drawn? And what is the duration of this process? The answers to them are in this article. The main thing for parents, if any, is to keep in mind that it is necessary to visit a pediatric dentist twice a year to undergo a preventive examination to identify problems in a timely manner. This will keep your child's teeth beautiful and healthy. Every parent wants their child's teeth to be healthy. To do this, they need to know how to properly

care for the oral cavity. With the appearance of the first tooth, you need to start hygiene. After all, it is necessary to keep all dairy products healthy, since caries negatively affects the local population. To do this, you need to familiarize yourself with the main aspects of care. How to brush teeth of a 1-year-old child.

You can tear the milk tooth both in the dentist's office and at home. At the same time, it is necessary to pay attention not only to the fact that the procedure is painless. However, tooth extraction is also an operation. Therefore, it should be carried out subject to all the rules of asepsis and antiseptics. Almost every baby begins to release milk teeth before the age of one year. A few years later, at the age of five or six, the child begins a serious and responsible period when the first milk teeth are replaced by permanent teeth. It is known that children's Milk Teeth also have roots, but the latter begin to dissolve gradually at a certain point.

Wisdom teeth appear in adults at different times, sometimes causing unbearable pain along with fever. The entire process of growth of wisdom teeth occurs in stages, only after the loss of milk teeth, when permanent teeth appear. It takes a different amount of time for each person.

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